

USAF AERONAUTICAL SYSTEMS DIVISION'S MODEL MANPOWER, PERSONNEL, AND TRAINING ORGANIZATION -- AN UPDATE

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ABSTRACT

Based on the critical need to enhance consideration of manpower, personnel and training (MPT) factors early in the weapon system acquisition process (WSAP), the United States Air Force established a model MPT integration organization at the Aeronautical Systems Division (ASD) at Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio. This organization was created by a memorandum of agreement between Air Staff (HQ USAF), Air Training Command (HQ ATC), and Air Force Systems Command (HQ AFSC). They dedicated 36 manpower positions to this purpose. The organization was chartered to study, recommend, and test ways that the Air Force's most expensive asset, people, can more fully affect weapon system design. Located within ASD's Deputate for Acquisition Logistics, the MPT Directorate has received initial staffing increments and has published its implementation plan. This paper has four major sections: (I) MPT integration problems to be solved, (II) MPT Process Objectives, (III) the new organization's mission and functions, and (IV) the latest update of the Directorate's concept of operation, including MPT analysis tools the Directorate could use.

SECTION I MPT INTEGRATION PROBLEMS TO BE SOLVED

While the United States Air Force (AF) led development of advanced analytic tools and data systems valuable for assisting MPT integration, it has not consistently applied available tools and data systems within a coherent framework. Beginning in the early 1980s, a number of studies and reports served to bring MPT problems into clearer focus. Prominent sources included:

- Defense Science Board Study in 1982
- Air Force (AF) contract studies
- GAO reports
- AF Functional Management Inspections (Jun 1986)

Findings from these sources and the realization that the Services were manpower-constrained intensified the sense of urgency to improve integration of MPT factors into the Air Force WSAP. As a result of these and other reports, investigations, and studies, the March 1986 MPT Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) was signed and the process of establishing the MPT Directorate was begun.

This summary of MPT integration problems to be solved is extracted from the MPT MOA and ASD/ALH implementation plan. These problems were drawn from the reports and studies listed above, and have been endorsed by the Colonel-level MPT Steering Committee, which oversees the Directorate's operation. The major MPT integration problems needing solution are listed below.

- o The Air Force WSAP needs a systematic approach to properly manage the integration of MPT factors.

- o MPT planning has generally been fragmented and ill-timed. One result is that actions to integrate MPT factors have not occurred early enough in the WSAP to influence the design. Usually, the major effort to analyze MPT impacts on weapon systems has taken place in the full-scale development phase after most life cycle costs are fixed.

- o The MPT planning effort often was not comprehensive enough to ensure that all pertinent factors were included or accurately applied. The Air Force did not clearly define weapon systems MPT goals for contractors designing and developing weapon systems. The initial estimates of manpower requirements needed to be identified as accurately as possible at the outset, with full consideration given to the specialties that will be involved in the new system.

- o Data for MPT analysis was not available in a usable format to analyze weapon system design and suggest trade-offs. On-line data transfer networks were not readily available to expedite data transfer.

- o Existing MPT requirements analysis tools were segmented and lacked the capability to do complete analyses to support complete MPT management decision process.

- o Training and training equipment were not being adequately or consistently funded, developed, and procured throughout the acquisition cycle concurrently with their weapon system.

- o MPT management was highly decentralized with no organization responsible for integrating and monitoring system related MPT requirements. Little effective direction and guidance was given to system program managers on MPT issues by Air Staff and the implementing commands (FMI finding).

- o Lack of controls over the MPT process resulted in duplication of effort, higher cost for weapon systems, and ill-defined and late-to-need aircrew and maintenance training equipment.

SECTION II

MPT PROCESS OBJECTIVES

To help the Air Force solve these problems and disconnects, the MPT directorate was chartered as a model organization with a mission to address these MPT process objectives contained in the MPT MOA and MPT Directorate Plan:

- o The primary objective of the MPT process is to improve analysis and integration of MPT issues in the acquisition cycle. MPT efforts must fully reflect the concerns and planning efforts of the using and supporting commands as well as the implementing command. To attain this objective the following sub-objectives must be met.

- Ensure that MPT factors and constraints are developed for use during early acquisition phases, where the potential to provide an optimally supported weapons system is greatest.

- Formulate a plan to bridge the gaps so MPT is factored into the acquisition process along with cost, schedule, performance, reliability, and maintainability; thus providing a more realistic, economical life-cycle cost for any given system in procurement or modification. MPT is a factor of weapon system supportability and needs to be highlighted as such.

- Ensure that training planning, requirements analysis, and training equipment development and production are planned, coordinated, and funded.

- Establish data sources, analytical tools, and procedures which support MPT trade-off analyses in the design of weapon systems.

- Make MPT analyses available in a format which emphasizes life-cycle cost-effective use of critical manpower, personnel and training resources.

SECTION III

MISSION AND FUNCTIONS OF THE MPT DIRECTORATE

The MPT Directorate's mission is to provide centralized planning, direction and control for all MPT elements in the ASD weapon systems acquisition process. Major functions include:

- o Directs the development and implementation of plans, policies and analytical tools to quantify MPT impacts on and of developing weapon systems. In this regard, the Directorate places special emphasis on front-end analysis to bring MPT into the forefront during initial design processes of Preconcept and Concept Phases of the WSAP.

- Reviews regulations, military standards (MIL STDs), and acquisition documents to ensure MPT integration is encouraged.

- Develops a detailed MPT management network plan for the ASD WSAP to identify the time-phasing and method of implementing critical MPT elements.

- Assists in defining MPT roles and functions of key ASD organizations to ensure full MPT integration in ASD's everyday conduct of business.

- o Employs analysis techniques and applicable policies and procedures to ensure consideration of alternative MPT utilization concepts and systems designs, and encourages necessary trade-offs to optimize cost and force effectiveness.

- o Maintains contact with Systems Program Offices, Deputates for Development Planning, Training Systems, Engineering and similar organizations to assure the Directorate's participation in their studies and analyses, ensuring MPT integration is included early and throughout the systems concept and design stages.

- o Maintains liaison with research organizations within and outside the military to optimize use of existing MPT resources; to promote research into areas beneficial to MPT; and thereby minimize costs for developing new models and systems to meet the organization's needs.

- o Functions as the ASD focal point in directing the activities of MPT analysts who are assigned to SPOs to advise, assist and provide technical information, appropriate analytical models, methodologies and information systems to support the MPT planning process on the selected weapon systems.

- o Provides the direction and leadership to obtain information systems equipment, software and related resources needed to support the Directorate's operations and MPT analyses.

- o Advises the ASD Commander and HQ AFSC through the Deputy for Acquisition Logistics (ASD/AL) on MPT matters.

- o Advises the MPT Steering Committee on the Directorate's progress in meeting the organization's objectives and obtains appropriate feedback for follow-on actions.

- o Maintains liaison with key AF MPT organizations, such as AFMPC, AF Manpower Engineering Agency, ATC, USAFOMC, and other Steering Committee offices to exchange MPT information, data and concepts.

- o Serves as the "model" Air Force MPT integration organization. Ensures that a comprehensive management plan is developed and updated with steps to achieve the organization's mission. The plan will provide detailed management information to similar organizations which may be established at the other AF product divisions. Further, ensures that MPT integration efforts are tracked by audit trails and evaluated to determine most effective methods and tools.

- o Publicizes MPT integration issues and successes using available publication media including news releases, news letters, briefings, etc.

SECTION IV

MPT DIRECTORATE PROPOSED CONCEPT OF OPERATION

INTRODUCTION TO CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS

Since its inception in September 1986, the MPT Directorate has been conducting studies and interacting with ASD organizations to establish roles and develop its concept of operation. In its April 1987 meeting the MPT Steering Committee approved the MPT Directorate's

draft plan, including the above mission and functions. In addition, the Committee endorsed briefings on ASD/ALH's preliminary concept of operation. Some aspects of this concept of operation will have to be more fully staffed before they become codified.

The remainder of this paper is intended to present a glimpse of the proposed ASD/ALH concept of operation. We believe that open discussion of this concept will help construct the most effective MPT organization. The concept of operation described below also includes the analysis tools and procedures which the MPT Directorate is strongly considering incorporating into ASD WSAP procedures.

The MPT Directorate's concept of operations, is described in terms of the following facets of ALH's given and planned activities. After a discussion of organizational placement, we'll look at some of the critical existing and proposed documents which can allow MPT to influence design. Third, we'll examine existing management tools which will give MPT visibility and help institutionalize MPT within the WSAP. Finally, since necessary actions differ during the various phases of the WSAP, we'll look at ALH's major proposed functions during the process.

FUNCTIONAL ALIGNMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

FUNCTIONAL ALIGNMENT OF ASD/ALH. The MPT Director is responsible to the Deputy for Acquisition Logistics (ASD/AL) oversight of activities of the home office and personnel matrixed to the program offices. Matrixed personnel are responsible to the Director for Manpower, Personnel, and Training, ASD/ALH, for MPT functions within ASD Acquisition Deputy organizations. This structure provides a central group of MPT personnel with visibility across program lines to ensure support and organizational objectives are attained; provides expertise for specific programs and/or issues during high demand periods (preparation and review of RFPs, SOWs, ITOs, etc.); and provides collocated MPT expertise to work the program-specific issues as the weapons system progresses through the acquisition process.

GENERAL CONCEPTS. The MPT Directorate will develop suitable data bases and analytical techniques to establish MPT constraints for the design process in much the same manner as performance and cost parameters are currently utilized. As a specific system transitions through the acquisition process, MPT Directorate personnel will aid the Systems Program Office (SPO) in establishing an MPT baseline, and will ensure all affected agencies are aware of the impacts upon that baseline as design, operational, or maintenance concept changes are proposed. The Directorate will address MPT supportability in both new and present acquisitions by providing both management guidance and technical support.

In a management role, the MPT Directorate will provide a means to formalize the MPT activities within SPOs. It is reviewing existing policy and will develop further guidance where appropriate. An essential management goal is to consolidate existing MPT direction and to provide a focal point for coordinating this direction.

In a technical support role, the MPT Directorate is responsible for providing program managers with MPT expertise. MPT analysts who are being matrixed to the SPOs will advise, assist, and provide technical information, appropriate analytical models, methodologies, and information systems to support the MPT planning process. These tools will be used to compare, project, and assess different design options and operational and maintenance scenarios for their relative MPT impacts and life-cycle costs. Maximum use will be made of currently available methodologies and tools such as Logistics Support Analyses (LSA), LSA Records (LSAR), appropriate LSA output reports, LCOM and Cost Oriented Resources Estimating (CORE) model outputs, and other life-cycle costs and MPT models. The MPT Directorate will develop contractual document statements which ensure that contractors are responsive to MPT concerns, and standards for evaluating MPT proposals during source selection.

PLAN / ROADMAP. The home office manpower, personnel, training, and analyst personnel, through a study in the WSAP methods, procedures, and tools, developed an implementation plan which describes its approach to MPT integration. In essence, this plan shows how the Directorate will develop its concept of operation. The plan received Air Force-wide feedback from offices concerned with MPT integration and was approved by the MPT Steering Committee in April 1987. The revised plan was published in August 1987 and is in the process of being implemented.

Essentially, the model program is being conducted in two distinct, yet interdependent stages: (1) MPT Development, and (2) MPT Implementation. The MPT Development stage encompasses the effort required to research, design, plan, and test an MPT strategy within the existing WSAP; this is the stage which the Directorate has now completed. The MPT Implementation stage, into which the Directorate is now proceeding, takes the MPT strategy and implements it in the major weapon system acquisition process.

MPT STEERING COMMITTEE. In consonance with the MPT objectives established in the MPT MOA, the Colonel-level Steering Committee provides a working forum for development of the model MPT program. It provides guidance, feedback, planning assistance, visibility, helps work issues, and assesses progress. It conducts semiannual reviews of all aspects of the model program and provides assessments to the MOA signatories. New emphasis has been placed on involving the using MAJCOMs in this committee.

ALH SPO-MATRIXED PERSONNEL. ASD/ALH has matrixed the first several MPT analysts to selected major weapon system SPOs, and will continue this process as additional matrixed personnel are selected and trained. The matrixed MPT analysts work for the Director of Logistics (DOL) to ensure MPT issues are fully addressed. Assisting the DOLs with manpower, personnel, and training expertise in working the Integrated Logistics Support (ILS) plan, they support the Chief Systems Engineer in identifying the full MPT ramifications of the various design issues faced by the SPO. They work interactively on all design issues having MPT implications, closely with SPO-matrixed engineering and logistics personnel. The matrixed MPT analysts are trained in manpower, personnel, training, WSAP, and basic MPT analysis techniques. When ALH is fully operational, approximately half of its 36 personnel will be matrixed to SPOs.

MPT DIRECTORATE HOME OFFICE SUPPORT. ASD/ALH's home office selects, trains and matrixes the MPT analysts to selected SPOs. ALH will also provide continuing training, advice and counsel. The home office is responsible for career enhancement, and supporting them on the more complex MPT analyses. For those SPOs not having matrixed personnel, ALH provides staff assistance and MPT analysis on a space available basis.

COORDINATING AND ASSISTING ASD ORGANIZATIONS. Several key ASD organizations have a special relationship with ASD/ALH. These include ASD's Deputy for Engineering, Safety Office, Deputy for Training Systems, the Deputy for Development Planning, and the ATC Operating Location (OL) at ASD.

Deputy for Engineering (EN). Like ALH, EN also has matrixed engineers in the SPOs who are supported by the home office. Close coordination between ASD/ALH and EN needs to be maintained to ensure that MIL STDs and procedures are developed which encourage MPT influence on design. Interaction is especially close with EN human factors, training, and LCOM personnel.

Safety Office (SE). SE also has matrixed system safety engineers and managers in the SPOs who are supported by their home office. Close coordination between ASD/ALH and SE will be maintained to ensure that safety programs and analyses are developed which encourage MPT influence on design. Interaction will be especially close with safety training and design hazard analyses to identify high drivers.

Deputy for Training Systems (YW) and the ATC OL (TTGT). ALH will also coordinate closely with YW (formerly SIMSPO) and with the ATC OL to ensure training systems developed to support aircraft systems LSA and engineering data are available in sufficient time to develop training systems that will be fielded with the weapon system.

Deputy for Development Planning (XR). ALH will be active during the WSAP phases in which design can be most influenced. Therefore, ALH is participating with the Development Planning Deputate on Long-Term Planning Projects that have potential MPT implications. Examples of these projects include the High Reliability Fighter, Embedded Trainer Concept, Recce-Attack Fighter Training System, etc. Matrixing an MPT analyst to this Deputate is helping to ensure that MPT factors are considered early in the acquisition process.

MAJCOM COORDINATION. In keeping with AF Systems Command policy, ALH is closely coordinating plans for using MAJCOM involvement in the MPT acquisition process with the MPT Steering committee. HQ USAF/PRM has tasked the using MAJCOM to consolidate manpower estimates prior to Milestones II and III to satisfy the 1987 Defense Authorization Bill's reporting requirements. Therefore, prime contractor, AF Logistics Command, SPO, and Air Training Command manpower requirements will be provided to the using MAJCOM. The using MAJCOM will be responsible for forwarding a consolidated statement of manpower requirements to HQ USAF, who forwards them through the Office of the Secretary of Defense to Congress. Close cooperation between ASD/ALH, ASD/EN, the SPO, and MAJCOMs is essential to ensure these important estimates are accurate. It is important that

these key players work together to ensure the best chance of achieving an optimum balance between manpower and equipment costs and of influencing design.

WEAPON SYSTEM ACQUISITION DOCUMENTS

The Weapon System Acquisition Process (WSAP) is a complex set of procedures controlled by several key documents. ASD/ALH plans to integrate MPT by reviewing, recommending changes, and ensuring the MPT aspects of these documents are prepared in sufficient time to affect design. These reviews will be conducted in conjunction with ASD/EN/YW/SE/XR counterparts.

EARLY ACQUISITION REQUIREMENT DOCUMENTS. ALH will review early acquisition documents to ensure MPT requirements and issues are appropriately addressed. The goal is to be proactive in setting specifications for design which require MPT trade-off analyses to construct systems which comply with MPT constraints. ALH will work with Air Staff, using MAJCOMs, the ASD staff, ATC, AFMPC, and ASD/EN (as appropriate) to ensure MPT constraints and goals are clearly communicated in early acquisition documents.

These documents include the Statement of Operational Need (SON), System Operational Requirements Documents (SOR), Requests for Proposal (RFPs), and Statements of Work (SOWs). MPT constraints, goals, issues, analyses and concerns need to be included in these documents if design is to be affected. Ultimately, the prime contractors must see the benefit of applying good MPT techniques in design. For this reason, ASD/ALH plans to furnish representatives for source selection, and ultimately develop generic MPT criteria which can be used as a guide for source selection of individual systems.

EXISTING ACQUISITION PLANS. In addition to acquisition documents and source selection, these acquisition plans include MPT information: the Human Factors Engineering (HFE) plan, the Integrated Logistics Support Plan (ILSP), the Training Development Plan (TDP) and the Test and Evaluation Master Plan (TEMP). ALH intends to improve the accuracy and completeness of MPT information in these documents. Also, ALH will attempt to ensure that MPT information is entered sufficiently early to allow design changes.

PROPOSED SYSTEM MPT PLAN. One way to ensure integration of MPT goals and constraints is to develop a weapon system MPT plan prior to Milestone 0. This kind of document could be developed by a team of MPT players to focus attention on MPT issues. The Systems MPT Plan could be a living document produced/revised (as a minimum) before each milestone, examining MPT issues which come to light as more is learned about the system. It would be designed to coordinate M, P, and T issues and goals for the system into an integrated approach. Further, this proposed plan would address ways in which MPT will be integrated into system design considerations.

Establishes MPT Constraints & Provides Visibility. In the initial phases of acquisition, the System MPT Plan could document the MPT constraints and goals for the system. Later, the plan could document trade-off decisions between M, P, and T, and between MPT and system performance/cost/schedule and other

considerations, giving visibility to MPT issues. The MPT plan could be coordinated among major MPT and system players, and be coordinated with the Human Factors, System Safety, Integrated Logistics Support (ILS) and Training Development Plans (TDP).

Add M & P to TDP. Because there are so many acquisition plans, often presenting the same or similar information, it would be best to avoid proliferation of plans. It is possible to expand an already existing plan, the TDP, for MPT purposes. The System MPT Plan could be composed of M and P issues added to the Training Development Plan. The Systems MPT Plan would start before Milestone 0, much earlier than the Training Development Plan (TDP) currently is begun. Expanding the TDP appears to make sense, since many critical MPT issues are already required in the TDP, yet are not developed soon enough to affect design.

Character Changes with Phases of WSAP. The character of the Systems MPT Plan would change as the weapon system matures. Initial editions would focus on MPT goals and constraints, with later versions focusing on system trades and a full-fledged Training Development Plan.

System MPT Planning Team. A System MPT Planning Team would be established for selected programs before Milestone 0. The team could be chaired by ALH until the SPO is staffed. Since the SPO Director is chair of the Training Planning Team (AFR 50-8), this Director should probably chair the System MPT Team. He/she will likely use the ALH SPO-matrixed person to work MPT plan issues and to document the System MPT Planning Team recommendations.

Team Composition Changes with WSAP. Before Milestone 0, proposed members of the System MPT Planning Team include the ASD MPT Directorate, Developmental Plans Deputate, ATC, AFMPC, the Using MAJCOM, and Air Staff Manpower and Personnel Plans. After staffing of the SPO (around Milestone 0), ASD Engineering and MPT Directorate SPO-matrixed personnel, the Deputy Program Manager for Logistics (DPML), and eventually the Prime Contractor(s) join, as ASD Developmental Plans and Air Staff agencies reduce their involvement. Later in the acquisition process, the team may also include the Air Force Operational Test and Evaluation Center (AFOTEC) to ensure appropriate test planning of MPT issues. The initial Systems MPT Plan can furnish needed input for the TDP and the MPT parts of the ILS plan. As the Training Planning Team is formed, meetings could be held in conjunction with the System MPT Planning Team meetings.

REGULATORY GUIDANCE. Finally, ALH plans to review the host of acquisition, manpower, personnel and training regulations to determine consistency and their impact on MPT integration. In addition, the Military Standards (MIL STDs) or Military Primes (MIL PRIMES) and Data Item Descriptors (DIDs) furnish guidance to contractors and writers of contracts. A thorough review and necessary revision will greatly facilitate MPT integration.

AUTOMATED DESIGN TOOLS AS MIL STDs. In place of MIL STDs, the new Computer Aided Design (CAD) system human factor design tools like Crew Chief and COMBIMAN can impact on prime contractor engineers while they are in the design process. These

human factor automated design aids use a three dimensional manikin on the CAD screen, allowing engineers to "see" accessibility problems. By making these systems available to all prime contractors and requiring their use, many of the access problems experienced in the past can be overcome during the design process. ALH will encourage their use and standardization into the design process.

USE EXISTING MPT ANALYSIS TOOLS & DATA SOURCES / SYSTEMS

The Air Force has many valuable MPT analysis tools and data bases/systems which, if integrated and applied, could pay big dividends. For example, LCOM (the AF-approved manpower modeling) has been thoroughly validated to produce aircraft maintenance manpower assessments through simulation. For aircraft maintenance, this method is far superior to and more accurate than the Army and Navy HARDMAN procedures of adding task times. LCOM uses the Maintenance Data Collection (MDC) system to furnish the crew size, frequency and maintenance tasks times for each aircraft system. Before inputting these data into LCOM, the MDC data are operationally audited by manpower personnel for consistency and accuracy. MDC data offers hard maintenance data on predecessor systems, which can be used in LCOM simulations of future systems. The Advanced Personnel Data System (APDS) and Occupational Survey Program furnish comprehensive data on which tasks are performed by Air Force personnel. These data are available "on line" through the Occupational Research Data Bank. Logistics Support Analysis (LSA) and LSA Record (LSAR) are available from prime contractors, and could be requested sufficiently early to provide training developers with needed information in time to field training systems with the aircraft. Validated human factor tools, which have been applied for years to cockpit design, could be applied more fully to maintenance. And both safety and human factor data bases could be used to focus attention on MPT high drivers in time to affect design. Let's examine a few of these tools/data bases to obtain an image of how ALH envisages employing them.

LCOM AS AN ITERATIVE PROCESS AND SOURCE OF MAINTENANCE MANPOWER ESTIMATES. LCOM is used as a tool to identify MPT high drivers and aircraft maintenance manpower assessments throughout the WSAP. LCOM will be conducted at increasing levels of specificity from Preconcept sensitivity analyses on the predecessor system, to baseline system comparisons during Concept Development, to LCOM models based on HFE/LSA comparability input data during the Demonstration/Validation Phase and more final HFE/LSA/engineering data during Full Scale Engineering Development. It will be the recommended source of aircraft maintenance manpower estimates. ALH will be responsible for conducting or contracting the LCOM sensitivity analyses using predecessor system or generic data prior to the SPO being formed. Once the SPO has been formed, EN may conduct/contract for LCOM analyses on selected major weapon system as requested by the SPO. The LCOM model produced by the ASD/EN, ALH, SPO and MAJCOM OL personnel could be used for both manpower assessments and engineering analyses.

APDS & CODAP AVAILABLE THROUGH THE ORDB. The Air Force has one of the most sophisticated personnel data systems available in any Service. It can describe AF military personnel in great detail by career ladder and has great flexibility for data manipulation to answer MPT questions. Comprehensive Occupational Data Analysis Programs (CODAP) enables the USAF Occupational Measurement Center to describe the tasks and related task data about each AF career ladder. Again, these data are stored in a very flexible format. Both APDS and CODAP data bases feed the Occupational Research Data Bank (ORDB) which makes computer "runs" available through "on-line" modem access. The one drawback to these data is that they are presented by Air Force Specialty Code (AFSC), which may or may not be directly related to an aircraft system. Research is under way to alleviate this disconnect. Once this is accomplished, the rich AF personnel data resources can be made available for the personnel/AFSC analysis needed to input to the LCOM manpower analysis. Until that time, ALH hopes to use this data as best possible in a manual mode.

LSA / LSAR AND HFE TASK DATA ORDERED ITERATIVE AND SOURCE FOR TRAINING DEVELOPMENT. LSA/LSAR and HFE task data will be ordered iteratively throughout the WSAP beginning with milestone 0 to provide data for addressing MPT issues. It is critical that the users tailor what they need, specify when each delivery is to take place, and that the medium specified is the most efficient/effective for immediate use. Later in the WSAP, complete and accurate LSA/LSAR is needed to address training development issues. If it is late, the training development system cannot ensure adequately trained personnel for the Initial Operational Capability (IOC). In the past, LSA/LSAR has received low priority. ALH will attempt to give higher visibility to HFE and LSA through the System MPT Plan so that the Air Force buys a total weapon system, including everything necessary for trained personnel to operate, maintain, and support it when fielded.

HUMAN FACTORING OF MAINTENANCE TASKS. In the past, most human factors efforts centered around the cockpit and crew positions. Because of the expense and lessened availability of maintenance manpower, it is critical that we start assigning the same human factor priority to maintenance as we have crew positions. The result will be maintenance tasks and equipment which reduce manhour requirements per unit, and increase the efficiency of maintenance turn-around and wartime readiness of new systems.

COORDINATION WITH SAFETY AND HUMAN FACTORS INITIATIVES. Because some safety and human factors issues can have large MPT implications, close coordination with the ASD Human Factors Engineering (HFE) Branch and Safety Office is appropriate. Both human factors and safety data sources could help identify high driver MPT issues. ALH will work closely with these offices to develop data-based ways of identifying MPT issues of consequence. By supporting issues of common interest, the three offices have a better chance of obtaining SPO funding for necessary analyses and of gaining implementation of HFE, Safety, and MPT positions.

MPT MANAGEMENT ACTION

In addition to the above methods, which may have management implications, ALH plans to conduct the intensive search and development to develop a CSNAS (see below) Network for MPT. In addition when fully staffed, ALH will take on the mission of developing a three-tiered Systems MPT course, and will work with Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) and ASD acquisition courses for full inclusion of MPT principles.

DEVELOPMENT OF CSNAS NETWORK. ALH will conduct a thorough review of regulations, MIL STDs, MIL PRIMES, operating instructions, and MPT requirements working cooperatively with appropriate ASD, AFSC, AFALC and Air Staff organizations. Based on the findings of this review ALH will construct a Computer Supported Network Analysis System (CSNAS) model network. This computerized "PERT diagram" using the critical path method, provides SPOs with a government-owned project management tool which meets regulatory requirements for each major program to have a networking system. The computer network identifies critical actions over the development of each system, and allows the SPO to show impacts of program changes on the schedule using the critical path method. The MPT model ALH will develop will provide SPO personnel with a prototype of what they should accomplish regarding MPT in their program. They can tailor the prototype model to meet the unique facets of their program so that MPT becomes an integral part of their program's management. In a recent command policy letter, AF Systems Command (AFSC/PLL) recommended CSNAS as the preferred method to meet the requirement for SPOs to meet their automated networking analysis requirement. Thus, the MPT CSNAS model will provide guidance on the timing and procedures for implementing MPT within each program in a command-approved format.

SYSTEMS MPT COURSE. While attempts have been made, it is clear that a course which fully covers manpower, personnel and maintenance training (as well as operator training) needs to be developed. As funds and manpower become available, ALH plans to monitor the contract for a three-tiered MPT course. A short version would be tailored for senior AF and Industry. A more detailed and functionally-oriented course would address the needs of MPT managers, logistics, human factors, and other Air Force and Industry personnel. Finally, a detailed MPT analyst course is needed for the ALH, SPO-matrixed, and other personnel who are expected to conduct weapon systems MPT analysis.

UPDATE AFIT & ASD ACQUISITION COURSES. Working with AFIT and ASD training personnel, ALH will update the courses used to educate and train ASD personnel on the acquisition process. As regulatory guidance is published, these courses are normally updated. Therefore, as progress is made in updating

regulations and MIL STDs, they will be incorporated into the AFIT courses. Already, the Directorate is furnishing instructors to teach MPT integration aspects of AFIT WSAP courses.

WSAP TIMELINE ACTIONS

Another way to describe ALH's concept of operations is to look at the major functions ALH will perform, or ensure are performed by acquisition phase. These are the MPT Directorate's goals:

PRECONCEPT: Develop MPT constraints and goals, define problems to be solved with new system, identify MPT analyses and trades to be examined, examine new technologies, participate in planning projects, and develop source selection criteria.

CONCEPT: Explore MPT alternatives, examine implications of design trades, develop alternate MPT concepts, influence design, and develop defined source selection criteria.

DEMONSTRATION / VALIDATION: Evaluate MPT implications of alternative systems, recommend changes, refine MPT concept, help refine manpower assessments, order data for training development, plan MPT tests, and develop source selection criteria.

FULL SCALE DEVELOPMENT: Evaluate System for MPT issues, finalize and publicize MPT concept, ensure training system developed, help finalize manpower estimate, and evaluate MPT tests.

PRODUCTION / DEPLOYMENT: Review test results for MPT implications, evaluate engineering change proposals and modifications, develop MPT lessons learned, and validate MPT concept.

SUMMARY

The Manpower Personnel and Training Directorate was established to test whether a long-standing need to fully integrate MPT considerations into the acquisition process could be institutionalized by a model organization at the AFSC product division level. The initial cadre of 12 military personnel developed an MPT Implementation Plan which is

summarized above. The goal of the organization's concept of operation is to determine how existing MPT analysis tools, data sources and procedures can more fully improve consideration of MPT factors in the WSAP. The MPT Directorate is giving favorable consideration to using or ensuring use of LCOM, CODAP, HFE task analyses and CAD tools, and LSA/LSAR. In addition, it plans to review acquisition documents for inclusion of MPT requirements, and use CSNAS as a management prototype to encourage timely requesting of MPT analyses and data. Regulation and MIL STD changes coupled with a three-tiered Systems MPT course will help encourage acquisition managers to consider MPT. And finally, a Systems MPT Plan is proposed to integrate M, P, and T and give MPT the appropriate planning and visibility. With this tool, the SPO-matrixed MPT analysts will be able to obtain MPT goals and constraints to influence system design, and can highlight the important MPT issues within and outside the SPO.

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